

SERS Detection of Melamine

Students from NTU-RPI-DTU Innovation workshop

INTRODUCTION

In recent years toxic melamine has been added to various dairy products in order to boost the apparent protein content at a low cost.

Surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy has been shown to be a possible method for rapid detection of malicious melamine additives to dairy products.

Using state of the art Raman effect enhancing substrates developed at DTU Nanotech, we aim at developing a rapid method of detecting trace levels of melamine in various test solutions as well as dairy products.